

Trapping airborne insects aboard inter-island ships in the Philippine archipelago, with emphasis on the brown planthopper (BPH)

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We studied the movement of airborne insects in the Philippines by trapping them aboard interisland ships during four voyages each in 1979 to 1981 dry and wet seasons. The study traced interisland movement of the BPH.

Airborne insects were collected using 6 wind-propelled, cone-shaped nylon nets (0.5 m diam, 2 m long) and 4 cross-shaped sticky board traps (0.45 × 0.45 m). During each voyage, one net was installed at the bow, two at the yardarms of the

mast, two on each side of the flying bridge, and one at the stern. The sticky traps were operated from the front railing of the flying bridge. Traps were opened about 30 min after sailing from each port and closed about 30 min before docking. Insect catches were then placed in coded vials for later identification in the laboratory.

During the 8 voyages, 1,874 insects, 46 spiders, and an ixodid tick were collected. Dipterans (47.9%) were most numerous, followed by 31.4% hemipterans, 13.5% hymenopterans, 6.4% coleopterans, and 1.0% lepidopterans, orthopterans, a psocopteran, an embiopteran, and a collembolan. More arthropods (1,066 insects and 33 araneids) were trapped in wet season than in dry season (808 insects, 13 araneids, and an ixodid tick) (Table 1). Among the delphacids trapped, the whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* was most abundant,

followed by BPH and *Sogatodes pusanus* (Table 2).

Southwesterly winds, 23.6-33.2°C temperature, and 56.5-99% relative humidity prevailed in wet season. Calm to variable winds punctuated by northeasterly and southeasterly air currents, 22.4-34°C temperature, and 43.8-95.8% relative humidity prevailed in dry season.

The relatively higher insect catches in wet season indicate that warm, humid air masses are ideal for transporting insects over long distances in the Philippines. Sea between islands was not an effective barrier to migrant insects. The catches also indicate that the bulk of *N. lugens* originated from rice producing areas lying along the path of the southwest monsoon. □

Table 1. Arthropods caught in nylon nets and on sticky traps installed aboard interisland vessels sailing along different routes in the Philippine archipelago in 1979-81 dry and wet seasons.^a

Insect order	Insects caught					
	Dry season (4 voyages)		Wet season (4 voyages)		S 8 voyages	
	No.	%	No.	%	Total	%
Diptera	381	47.2	516	48.4	897	47.9
Hemiptera	204	25.2	384	36.0	588	31.4
Hymenoptera	131	16.2	122	11.4	253	13.5
Coleoptera	83	10.3	36	3.4	119	6.4
Lepidoptera	6	0.7	6	0.6	12	0.6
Orthoptera	1	0.1	1	0.1	2	0.1
Psocoptera	0	0	1	0.1	1	0.1
Embioptera	1	0.1	0	0	1	0.1
Collembola	1	0.1	0	0	1	0.1
	S	808	1066		1874	
Araneida	13		33		46	
Acari	1		0		1	

^aRoutes and duration of each voyage during dry and wet seasons. *Dry season*: I. Manila-Cagayan de Oro-Manila, 26 Jan-2 Feb 1980, II. Manila-Iligan-Manila, 7-15 May 1980, III. Manila-Cagayan de Oro-Manila, 14-22 Feb 1981, IV. Manila-Cagayan de Oro-Manila, 21-29 May 1981. *Wet season*: I. Manila-Butuan-Manila, 27 Jun-6 Jul 1979, II. Manila-Iligan-Manila, 3-11 Oct 1979, III. Manila-Iligan-Manila, 15-24 Jul 1980, IV. Manila-Iligan-Manila, 17-25 Oct 1980.

Table 2. Delphacids caught in nylon nets and on sticky traps installed aboard interisland vessels sailing along different routes in the Philippine archipelago during 1979-81 dry and wet seasons.

Species	Insects caught (no.)	
	Dry season (4 voyages)	Wet season (4 voyages)
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	1	22
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	8	35
<i>Euidellana</i>	0	1
<i>Harmalia anocharsis</i>	1	0
<i>Harmalia nr. heitensis</i>	1	0
<i>Harmalia</i> spp.	1	2
<i>Nilaparvata bakeri</i>	2	2
<i>Nilaparvata</i> spp.	2	3
<i>Opiconsiva dodona</i>	2	0
<i>Opiconsiva</i> sp.	0	1
<i>Perkinsiella</i> sp.	0	1
<i>Sogatella eupompe</i>	0	1
<i>Sogatella kolophon</i>	0	2
<i>Sogatella panicicola</i>	2	3
<i>Sogatella terryi</i>	0	1
<i>Sogatella</i> spp.	0	7
<i>Sogatodes pusanus</i>	0	11
<i>Sogatodes</i> sp.	0	2
<i>Toya</i> close to <i>propinqua</i>	0	1
Unidentified delphacids	1	14
	S21	108

Influence of light traps on incidence of yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* Wik. in the trap zone and field

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We studied the influence of a light trap on YSB infestation in surrounding fields. A Robinson light trap with a 125-W mercury lamp was operated from Dec 1981 to Feb 1982 on the Agricultural College Farm, Madurai, during which time YSB incidence was high. The trap operated from 1800 to 0600 h in a field cropped with IR20.

Each morning, 10 hills were randomly selected at 1 m from the trap and the number of YSB on the hills was estimated. Counts were made for 2 wk during peak infestation.

There was a significantly positive correlation ($r = 0.79$) between the number of YSB on 10 hills and the daily light trap catch (Table 1). Moths which were at-

tracted to the light but did not enter the trap settled near it. Because moths are nocturnal, movement ceased after day-light.

We compared deadheart and whitehead incidence by selecting 10 hills in diagonal lines at 1, 5, 10, and 20 m from the trap, and in fields located far away from the light traps where the light could not be seen by YSB. As distance from the light trap increased, percent deadhearts declined (Table 2).

The increased infestation at 1 m around the trap was due to the settlement of YSB. Moths also may have migrated to surrounding areas during the day and caused more damage in that area as indicated by higher incidences even at the distance of 10 m. Our data indicate it may be wise to spray around the trap area with a suitable insecticide to reduce field damage. □

Table 1. Relation between light trap catch and settlement of YSB around the trap, Madurai, India.

Date	Moths settled (no./10 hills)	Light trap catch (no.)
8 Dec 1981	63	242
9 Dec 1981	71	387
10 Dec 1981	68	342
11 Dec 1981	61	288
12 Dec 1981	51	220
13 Dec 1981	97	620
14 Dec 1981	81	420
15 Dec 1981	88	580
16 Dec 1981	32	36
17 Dec 1981	28	42
18 Dec 1981	31	86
19 Dec 1981	48	108
20 Dec 1981	58	280
21 Dec 1981	73	460

$r = +0.79^{**a}$

^aSignificant at 1% level.

Table 2. YSB incidence at different distances from the light trap, Madurai, India.

Date	Incidence (%)				
	1 m	5 m	10 m	20 m	Light shadow region
15 Dec 1981	22	20	11	6	7
22 Dec 1981	36	24	18	13	14
29 Dec 1981	57	49	37	23	24
6 Jan 1982	59	50	39	25	27
13 Jan 1982	67	52	43	26	29
20 Jan 1982	74	55	46	29	32
24 Jan 1982	82	57	46	29	31
3 Feb 1982	86	21	14	12	13
10 Feb 1982	91	24	15	12	15
17 Feb 1982	100	28	18	15	17
Meananalysis	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅

F = 24.07^{**a}
CD (P = 0.05) = 7.55

^aSignificant at 1% level.

Population density of *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) (WBPH) and *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal.) (BPH)

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We compared changes in population density of WBPH and BPH in the greenhouse at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore. In 4 experiments with 12 replications, combinations of WBPH and BPH were placed on individually caged 30-d-old potted TN1 plants as follows: 10 WBPH and 10 BPH first instar nymphs; 10 WBPH and 20 BPH; 20 WBPH and 10 BPH; and 1 WBPH and 1 BPH brachypterous female. Insect population was monitored for three generations.

WBPH population increased more rapidly than that of BPH in all the experiments (see figure). There was no significant difference in population level during the first 2 generations when 10 first-instar nymphs of both species and one brachypterous female of both species were confined together in different experiments. However, the differences were highly significant in experiments with different numbers of first-instar nymphs.

Population density of WBPH and BPH, Coimbatore, India.

WBPH and BPH populations declined after the second generation. Crop age may have favored the buildup of WBPH over BPH, because BPH population usually increases after heading. The field population of WBPH usually is largest 70-90 d after seeding, which corresponds roughly with the age of TN1 plants during the third generation in this experiment. □

Electronically recorded disturbances in the feeding behavior of green leafhopper (GLH) on neem oil-treated rice plants

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We electronically recorded aberrations in GLH feeding behavior on neem oil-treated rice plants.

A fine (1.8 mμ), 5-cm-long gold wire was attached by silver paint to the dorsum of an 8- to 10-h-old GLH female. The insect was starved for 2 h and then its normal feeding activity was recorded electronically for 180 min using a D. C.